

Supplementary Figure 4: Epifluorescence microscopy images of enzyme protection assays. A & B) Negative and positive control showing cells grown on YM and cells incubated in FLA-YM. **C & D)** FLA-YM stained cells incubated in YM specific enzymes. **E)** FGC treated with YM-specific enzymes before incubation with *B. theta*. Exposure times are consistent between images and signal loss represents depletion of FLA-YM. Scale bar = 5 μ m.